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NEWS

Visual Astronomy Display: October 2014

Katie Frey Updated on August 24, 2022 Leave a Comment

Visual Astronomy Display for October 2014

Highlights...

- SciShow ponders the famous statement from Carl Sagan that “we are made of star-stuff”, exactly how much of us really is “star-stuff”?;
- Nature published a short video about **Laniakea, our home supercluster**, and the team of scientists who discovered it;
- **Philae prepares to land on the surface of comet 67P/Churyumov–Gerasimenko** in November 2014;
- After months of travel, **Curiosity finally arrives at Mount Sharp!** NASA scientists are expecting to learn a lot about Mars by studying the geological features of Mount Sharp; and
- In related news, **India’s spacecraft, Mangalyaan, attains Martian orbit**, making India the first country to successfully reach Mars on it’s first attempt.

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Close-up view of the globular star cluster Messier 54

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Katie Frey leads the development of the Unified Astronomy Thesaurus, a community supported linked data vocabulary for sorting, filtering, and exploring astronomical literature, data sets, images, etc.

About Katie Frey

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